

WHAT COMES AFTER?

BEYOND4.0 supports an inclusive European future via examining the impact of Industrie4.0 and the Digital disruption on the future of jobs, business models and welfare.

POLICY BRIEF #5

Understanding Technological Revolutions: Why history matters

November 2021

BEYOND4.0 supports the delivery of an inclusive future of decent work and decent lives for EU citizens. This Policy Briefing focuses on how previous technological revolutions are understood and why this understanding impacts policy design in the present. Each such revolution has required deep changes in government, institutions, and policies to shape the new technologies for the benefit of both business and society. The Policy Brief outlines the cyclical patterns of the relationship between technology, society, finance, government and the economy. History shows that the development and diffusion of each new technology follows a context-dependent direction. Currently, evidence suggests that the direction today should be 'smart' green, fair and global. In this Policy Brief, the positives and negatives of the different approaches to policymaking are summarised and recommendations offered based on the historical experience:

- Develop deeper understanding of the transitional nature of the current moment: the post-Covid recovery cannot look back to 'business as usual', but must act innovately
- Grow more confidence in the key role that government plays in fostering a direction for the deployment of new technological potential that is win-win for business and society
- Reject or rethink obsolescent government structures and methods to match the technological potential of the present moment
- Set specific 'missions' at all levels of government to achieve social and environmental sustainability
- Support education systems, recognizing that human capital is now the most valuable asset for both citizens and countries
- Rethink globalised trade and industrial strategies, increasing national manufacturing response capacity and resilience
- Regulate finance and the new tech giants

Background to Policy Brief #5

BEYOND4.0 examines the impact of new digital technologies on the future of jobs, business models and welfare in the European Union (EU). It aims to support an inclusive European future that provides decent work and decent lives for EU citizens.

BEYOND4.0 takes its name from the term 'Industrie 4.0', used as a shorthand to describe the use in production of the new digital technologies (see Policy Brief #2). Despite its acceptance, the notion that we are in a '4th Industrial Revolution' is a recent one, and the definition of what makes such a revolution is not clear. Indeed, even the term 'industrial' is misleading: the revolutionary transformations in organisations, processes and lifestyles across society are not limited to industry but are more accurately described as 'technological revolutions'. There have been many attempts to identify such techno-economic cycles in the history of capitalism. The current debate is dominated by the 'techno-optimist' and 'techno-pessimist' camps, each with a different narrative about the impact of new technologies on our future and how policymakers can boost the benefits while mitigating the destruction of skills, employment and livelihoods.

This Policy Brief focuses on the different ways in which technological revolutions have been studied and understood historically. While some attempts have been made to outline definitive historical periods with categorical empirical evidence, they have not produced tight conclusions. This Policy Brief is different. It summarises the study of economic cycles and the history of previous transformations and critically outlines the benefits and limitations of essentially conceptual frameworks. It proposes complementing Schwab's '4th Industrial Revolution' approach with the neo-Schumpeterian scholarship, which highlights the crucial role that governments play in the successful deployment of new socio-technical systems. At the same time, it offers recommendations for policymakers on how to understand the past so that policy can be better designed to ensure that the new technologies deliver a socially and environmentally sustainable future.

Techno-optimists, pessimists – or determinists: how many revolutions, and why it matters

Policy-makers and academics now recognise that technological innovation is a key driver of progress. Nevertheless, neither policy-makers nor academics really go beyond a general notion of innovation and fully understand how technologies evolve, inter-relate and are absorbed, shaped, and diffused across society and the economy. What is gaining ground is the recognition that technological advance is not continuous but is rather revolutionised every time the economy confronts maturity by a series of interrelated innovations that explode and lead to periods of 'creative destruction'. Such transitions result in times of rise and fall in economic growth.

In this regard, the idea that we are currently in the '4th Industrial Revolution' has come to dominate both policy and academic discourse. The term was first used to describe the technological upgrading of manufacturing in Germany and then championed by Klaus Schwab of the World Economic Forum at the annual meetings in Davos. However, the academic literature and the current business debate around technological revolutions and their diffusion identify different numbers of revolutions and diverging interpretations of their nature and consequences.

These interpretations can be categorised into a number of broad approaches by discipline and perspective. Very basic revolutionary periodisations identify transformational points primarily by the 'big bang' of inventions – the spinning jenny, steam engine, Ford Model-T and computer for example. The econometric tradition focuses on economic cycles and long waves (so-called 'K-waves', after the pioneering economist Nikolai Kondratiev) shown in the upswings and downswings of GDP and other statistical variables. These data-driven analyses tend to search for empirical 'proof' of these waves, focused narrowly on the causes of the change in the variables. Economic historians and others with a socio-historical approach take a broader view of the causes of these technological changes and the consequences that these transformations bring across society. For example, those in the neo-Marxist tradition examine how technologies shape power relations in the production and distribution processes. Other commentators from business, management and engineering backgrounds focus on changes in methods of production or organisation and on the future of employment and skills; the four revolutions of Industrie 4.0 are one such example, likewise the 'two machine ages' of Brynjolfsson and McAfee.

Many of these current commentators concentrate on the initial – and often negative – consequences of the new digital technology, whether that be standards of living and/or employment. Even if they are generally positive about the future, this focus holds and is working to mitigate the negative effects. Notably, both techno-pessimists and optimists have the tendency – if unwittingly – to be deterministic about the technology. The way they frame previous transitions means that they do not recognise the capacity or the need for government policy to shape the course of technologies, which in their view, is inexorable. Policy recommendations that emerge from these commentators' work are little more than bolt-ons to business as usual to a model that derives from the previous mass production era.

By contrast, Schwab and other advocates of the '4th Industrial Revolution' represent a shift in thinking. They take a more proactive, non-deterministic stance that recognises the complexity of

interactions between technologies old and new and the role and impact of multiple actors across society. Although missing the solid grounding of a historical model of how technological change takes place and why and how society has absorbed and shaped similar transformations in the past, they signal the need for debate to move on from a modified business-as-usual perspective to the need for a more radical 'Great Reset'.

Neo-Schumpeterian economists such as Perez, a co-author of this Policy Brief, provide such a historical model. They analyse the feedback loops of transformation between science, technology, the economy, society and politics. Based on such a reading of the historical record, and at the same time building on the work of the long wave scholars, their analysis puts us at the mid-point of the 5th or ICT-driven revolution, as the next section explains. This position can be complemented by the Dutch Transitions school, which provides a theory-driven model of socio-technical transformations that takes into account norms, organisational forms and government policy. For the most part, their model focuses on institutional shifts at the meso-level. A much broader view, encompassing the world economy, is taken by Kanger and Schot, who, taking the Neo-Schumpeterian model into account, argue for a deep transition across society, seeing the present green transition as equivalent to the first industrial revolution.

The neo-Schumpeterian approach: the social shaping of technology

The strength of neo-Schumpeterian research on technological revolutions is that it identifies recurring structures and a regular sequence in the diffusion process and the form of absorption of change by the economy, society and policy (see below Figure 1). This historical regularity enables identification of the point of crucial policy action. Importantly for policymakers, the long-term

record shows that, after a period of financialised diffusion of the new technologies, with increasing inequality, jobs and skills destruction and financial bubbles and crashes, government policy works to bring in golden ages. The State has regularly intervened to shape the direction, not only of the new technologies but also of the new lifestyles and complementary industries.

Neo-Schumpeterian research also suggests that each set of new technologies leads to a new common sense for innovation and investment – a techno-economic paradigm – that is eventually shared by innovators,

entrepreneurs, bankers, investors, consumers and government. However, it is only after a turbulent period of replacement of one set of technologies by another, and once a bubble (or two as in recent years) has swelled and burst, that the painful social consequences of that transformation forced by finance become evident to all. At this point, the destruction side of Schumpeter's 'creative destruction' becomes starkly visible. Anger and resentment create conditions for populism to gain support; political parties divide, and new political movements emerge.

At this moment in the diffusion process, the time comes for the return of proactive government policies to give an appropriate direction to the new technologies now that their positive and negative effects are fully understood. In doing so, the government can better counter the worst trends and impacts that have emerged in the initial decades of the technology's emergence. Historically, an important aspect of this 'turning point' is the shift of control from financial to production capital with the support of the State, which then effectively regulates finance to avoid its tendency to become a self-centred casino and induce it to fund the real economy. Another aspect of the shaping process is the regulation of the major monopolies that tend to emerge at this time, securing competition, consumer protection and stakeholder fairness.

Figure 1: The recurring pattern of diffusion of technological revolutions

Source: Perez and Murray Leach (2021).

These interventions have unleashed the golden ages of the Victorian Boom, the Belle Époque and the Post-War Boom (see below Figure 2). During the last turning point in the 1930s, the necessary political momentum to bring back proactive governments was generated by World War II. Now, as Schwab and others recognise, the need for cooperation for such a 'great reset' is driven by the ecological emergency and the COVID-19 crisis.

Using history to understand technological revolutions past and present, it is possible to engage in a major set of policy innovations capable of bringing about a socially and environmentally sustainable global golden age for the Information Era. It is not about replacing the market or picking winners but rather about tilting the playing field in desirable directions inducing innovation and investment into a synergistic process of mutually enhancing supply and demand. The result can be a positive-sum game between business, society and the planet.

It should be noted that, the same set of technologies can be given different directions by different countries with equivalent success, depending on their circumstances. For example, during the heavy engineering or 3rd Industrial Revolution, Britain was Queen of the Seas and thriving as the global financial power. Government action at that time was to enable 'free markets', including building the infrastructure (global railways, telegraph ports, steamships etc.) to facilitate it. In the meantime, Germany and the US were catching up and trying to forge ahead, adopting strong protectionism to unify their economic space while elevating their human capital, massively investing in science, technology and education, as well as modernising agriculture and industry to achieve competitiveness. Yet, the US tended towards consumer good and Germany towards capital goods. By the next revolution, they had reached enough similarity for all three countries, after

World War II, to apply variations of the same directionality to the mass-production revolution: towards suburbanisation, consumerism and the Cold War.

What is important to realise is the amount of institutional innovation that accompanied each golden age. For example, the Post War boom was underpinned by different models of the Welfare State, multiple ways to provide the new infrastructures and to promote and support homeownership while the international order was maintained by the rise of multilateral organisations such as the IMF, World Bank, GATT and UN.

Tilting the playing field to guide innovation and investment is once more the task at hand. Now, achieving a more ethical and balanced, socially and environmentally sustainable capitalism will again imply massive institutional imagination and

innovation. That is the challenge that the study of technological revolutions presents to policymakers today and the optimistic, yet demanding, message it provides.

Policy Implications and Recommendations

The European Commission has already identified the major challenges facing the Member States and the world from climate change and social inequality. It also prioritises innovation, especially ICT and the current 5th technological revolution (or its expression in Industrie 4.0). It is confronting the pandemic with extraordinary interventions in the economy and implementing a Recovery Plan. It has set up a Green Deal Investment Plan and the Just Transition Mechanism, which are on track to shape the future in that direction. The EU has thus shown that it is ready to make the systemic leap into shaping the ICT revolution in a smart, green, fair and global growth direction, across society and the economy. And understanding of the ICT revolution and the history of such transitions show that making such a leap will require a major effort in institutional innovation:

1. *Develop deeper understanding of the transitional nature of the current moment: the post-Covid recovery cannot look back to 'business as usual', but must act innovately*

Since the 'double bubble' and crashes around the turn of the century, we have been in the turning point of a technological transition, but have remained stuck in attempting to 'fix' the increasing obsolescence of the previous mass production revolution. At all levels of government, from local to national to supranational, the post-Covid Recovery Plan and reconstruction therefore should be understood not as going back to business as usual but as an opportunity to 'reset' the EU and its Member States in alignment with the current moment, moving forward rather than clawing at the past.

2. *Grow more confidence in the key role that government plays in fostering a direction for the deployment of new technological potential that is win-win for business and society*

It is important that politicians, civil servants and civilians alike have a deeper understanding of the historic roles of both government and business/finance in innovation and economic development, rather than getting polarised in an oppositional binary. This will allow policy-makers to confidently legislate in a similar manner to those who designed the post-WWII recovery at the turning point of the previous techno-economic transition, and provide a clear environmentally sustainable and socially fair direction for investment and innovation in our new technological era. The Green Deal Investment Plan and the Just Transition Mechanism are on track to shape the future in that direction.

3. Reject or rethink obsolescent government structures and methods to match the technological potential of the present moment.

To shape the current technological potential, governments also need to shape themselves accordingly. It is important to address legacy challenges from the Fordist era in how government operates. It will be necessary to rethink and update the organisation and methods of government, aiming to make it as easy to use as Amazon, as agile as the most creative companies and as empowering for citizens and workers as the most successful cooperatives and networks. It is not about simply digitalising government but about taking advantage of the revolutionary nature of digital technologies whilst simultaneously enabling workers to be innovative.

4. Set specific 'missions' at all levels of government to achieve social and environmental sustainability

Within the context of the two major goals identified by the European Commission as urgent – social and environmental sustainability – the task in all countries and at all levels is to identify 'missions' around specific issues that will unleash the potential of the new technology. Differences in local, national and regional circumstances must be reflected, and self-determination encouraged and respected. The goals can then be broken down into plans that, within the action space of each government, can engender cooperation between actors and across different industries to achieve job creation and with more equitable wage outcomes.

5. Support education, recognising that human capital is now the most valuable asset for citizens and countries

To get the best social outcome from the Information Era, the education system must be supported with the same intensity as homeownership was during the mass production golden age. The capacity for and the accumulation of science, technology, education and skills are now the equivalent of physical infrastructure in past epochs. A growth policy that is not embedded in innovation and education strategies cannot succeed. The government at all levels needs to reflect that understanding, including the European Commission. Therefore, encouraging the Member States to support the enhancement of human capital and to facilitate access for all without burdening young people with debt is an urgent and important task. The education of each now brings benefits to all.

6. Rethink globalised trade and industrial strategies, increasing national manufacturing response capacity and resilience

The new paradigm is globalising by nature. It comes with the capacity to transmit information instantly across borders and to support complex value chains. The globalisation issue is at the centre of policies designed to shape the new technologies. One of the legacies of the pandemic has been to discover the lack of strategic thinking and attention to the resilience (or not) of

globalisation. Instead, market forces have been left to prevail. A simplistic emphasis on cost reduction has left many developed countries unable to respond to manufacturing emergencies directly. At the same time, the loss of jobs and skills from technical change and globalisation has created resentment and fuelled populism, which has been exacerbated by the immigration from poorer or war-torn countries. The European Commission and the European Parliament need to confront both these issues and agree on a strategic set of goals and criteria for a dynamic, fair and even more global economy that delivers a positive-sum game for all countries. Europe is best placed to promote the creation of a global financial transactions tax to fund a global Green Development Bank, for example.

7. Regulate finance and the new tech giants

The initial decades of technological revolutions are characterised by financial bubbles and monopolies. Thus stringent and adequate regulation of finance has been the response, historically, to the financial crashes that tend to occur midway through the diffusion of each new technology. Intelligent and appropriate forms of control of both finance and the new giants are now needed to create better conditions for the real economy to flourish. Doing it well requires an understanding of the particular nature of the ICT giants, the specific threats presented by the new technology (AI, robotics, Internet of things, etc.), and the free and invisible movement of finance across the globe. The two previous technological revolutions regulated the monopolies of the time, but the policies used then are no longer applicable. The EU has a head start in regulation and experimentation, yet much more is needed to deal with the new monopolies with their winner-takes-all strategies, their intentional invasion of privacy and the various means of tax avoidance. Further technological and political understanding as well as imagination will be required to rein in finance and to orient and regulate the digital giants in a way that is effective and appropriate to their nature.

Authors

Carlota Perez with Tamsin Murray Leach of University College London in the UK.

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Project Details

Project name	Inclusive Futures for Europe BEYOND the impacts of Industrie 4.0 and Digital Disruption — BEYOND4.0
Coordinator	Prof. Dr Steven Dhondt (scientific coordinator), Dr Peter Oeij (project coordinator). Nederlandse Organisatie Voor Toegepast Natuurwetenschappelijk Onderzoek TNO, Netherlands
Consortium	Department of Social Research, University Of Turku, Finland Institute for Employment Research, University of Warwick, UK Institute for the Study of Societies and Knowledge, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (ISSK-BAS), Bulgaria Le CNAM-CEET, France Nederlandse Organisatie Voor Toegepast Natuurwetenschappelijk Onderzoek TNO, Netherlands Technische Universitat Dortmund, Sozialforschungsstelle Dortmund (sfs) (TUDO), Germany UCL Institute for Innovation and Public Purpose (IIPP), London, UK University of Helsinki, Finland University of the Basque Country - Sinergiak Social Innovation, Basque Country – Spain
Duration	2019 - 2023
Funding Scheme	Grant Agreement number: 822296 — BEYOND4.0 — H2020-SC6-TRANSFORMATIONS-2018-2019-2020/H2020-SC6TRANSFORMATIONS-2018
Budget	EUR 2,999,970.00
Website	www.beyond4-0.eu
Further reading	www.beyond4-0.eu/publications
For more information	contact@beyond4-0.eu, peter.oeij@tno.nl
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